

VII. APPENDIX

A. Additional descriptive statistics

TABLE III
REPRESENTATIVENESS STATISTICS

Sociodemographics	Absolute	Share	Official Statistic
Gender			
Male	507	50.2%	50.3%
Female	498	49.3%	49.7%
Other	6	0.5%	not reported
Age Class			
< 35 years	286	28.3%	28.7%
Between 35-64 years	544	53.8%	53.2%
> 64 years	181	17.9%	18.1%
Education Level			
Bachelor or below	776	76.8%	79.3%
Master or higher	235	23.2%	20.7%

Official Statistics to be found at STATEC⁵ and Statistiques.lu⁶, respectively

TABLE IV
ADDITIONAL DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS (N = 1,011)

Characteristic	Absolute	Share	Official Statistic
Dwelling Ownership			
Owning	820	81.1%	67.6%
Renting	191	18.9%	32.4%
Housing			
House	696	68.8%	59.2%
Apartment	315	31.2%	40.8%
Household Size			
1-4	923	91.3%	not reported
> 4	88	8.7%	not reported

Official Statistics to be found at Eurostat⁷ and Statistiques.lu⁸, respectively

TABLE V
INCOME STATISTICS (N = 1,011)

Household Type	Share	Median Income Class	Official Mean
Single household	13.8%	3,000-4,999 €	3,907 €
Couple household	28%	7,000-8,999 €	7,969 €
Family with kids	32.7%	7,000-8,999 €	8,603 €
Family without kids	24.5%	7,000-8,999 €	not reported
Non-family setting	1%	4,000-4,999 €	not reported

Official Statistics to be found at Eurostat⁹

TABLE VI
CONSTRUCT STATISTICS (N = 1,011)

Construct	Mean	Std. dev.	Min-Max
Pro-env. values	4.48	1.04	0-6
ERFL	3.67	1.89	0-8
PEL	2.76	1.2	0-5
PBC	3.973	0.96	0-6

⁵STATEC Population Data (DF_B1102)

⁶Statistiques.lu education levels

⁷Eurostat "Housing in Europe 2024 Edition"

⁸Statistiques.lu "N° 22 - La Ville de Luxembourg et sa périphérie"

⁹Eurostat "10.2908/EARN_NT_NET"

B. Extended results table

This appendix provides an extended version of Table II, reporting the full set of coefficients for all control variables in the averaged PBC models. Table VII presents the results for the average PBC using the combined ERFL measure, while Table VIII reports the specifications in which ERFL is decomposed into its FL and EL components. Across both models, age and income emerge as the only control variables with statistically significant associations with PBC. Environmental attitudes are also positively associated with PBC, whereas none of the literacy measures show significant effects.

In these tables, column (1) corresponds to a baseline specification including only environmental attitudes and literacy measures; column (2) augments this model with socio-demographic controls; and column (3) introduces household characteristics to form the full model. In both cases, we see that our findings on the explanatory variables (Environmental attitudes, ERFL, PEL, EL, and FL) stay consistent across all specifications.

TABLE VII
EXTENDED RESULTS TABLE WITH ERFL

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)
Env. attitude	0.1557***	0.1329***	0.1228***
Literacy			
PEL	0.0327	0.0215	0.0234
ERFL	-0.05953	-0.05433	-0.0411
Demographics			
Gender	✗	0.0442	0.0429
Age	✗	0.2061***	0.1933***
Education	✗	-0.05833	-0.0556
Income	✗	-0.1315***	-0.1310***
Households			
Hours at home	✗	✗	-0.0032
Household size	✗	✗	0.0093
Age of building	✗	✗	0.0556
Obs.	804	804	804

Notes: PEL = Perceived energy literacy. ERFL = Energy-related financial literacy.

Significance: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

C. Robustness Checks

To assess the robustness of our results, we repeated all regressions using the full initial dataset of 1,011 respondents. The results (shown in table IX) were highly consistent with those from the reduced dataset: the direction of the key relationships remained unchanged, and significant predictors stayed significant in the same direction. Although a few coefficients changed slightly in magnitude and some marginal effects moved just above or below conventional significance thresholds, these adjustments did not alter the overall pattern or interpretation of the results. This indicates that our findings are robust: the results do not depend on respondents with missing data, and the key relationships in our models remain stable across samples. This strengthens confidence in the internal validity of our conclusions.

TABLE VIII
EXTENDED RESULTS TABLE SEPARATING FINANCIAL AND ENERGY LITERACY

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)
Env. attitude	0.1557***	0.1248***	0.1236***
Literacy			
PEL	0.0327	0.0249	0.0225
EL	-0.0408	-0.0202	-0.0189
FL	-0.0308	-0.0294	-0.0329
Demographics			
Gender	X	0.0438	0.0423
Age	X	0.20757***	0.1951***
Education	X	-0.0575	-0.0544
Income	X	-0.1307***	-0.1298***
Households			
Hours at home	X	X	-0.0032
Household size	X	X	0.0092
Age of building	X	X	0.0556
Obs.	804	804	804

Notes: PEL = Perceived energy literacy. ERFL = Energy-related financial literacy. EL = Energy literacy. FL = Financial Literacy
Significance: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

TABLE IX
REGRESSION RESULTS FOR ACTION-SPECIFIC PBC MODELS AND MODELS SEPARATING LITERACY (N = 1,011)

Panel A: Model with ERFL				
Action (PBC)	Env. attitude	PEL	ERFL	
Total PBC	0.1467***	0.0454	-0.0712*	
Turning off lights	0.2510***	-0.0150	0.0763*	
Less use of washing machine	0.0660	0.0940*	-0.1484**	
Less use of tumble dryer	0.2057***	0.0867	0.0022	
Less use of dishwasher	0.0728	0.0359	-0.1285**	
Reduce hot showers	0.1126**	0.0595	-0.1376**	
Wash clothes at defined hours	0.1502***	0.0902*	-0.0365	
Dry clothes at defined hours	0.2292***	0.0075	-0.0224	
Wash dishes at defined hours	0.1706***	0.0282	-0.0807	
Hot showers at defined hours	0.0620	0.0211	-0.1652***	

Panel B: Model separating financial and energy literacy				
Action (PBC)	Env. attitude	PEL	FL	EL
Total PBC	0.1482***	0.0438	-0.057	-0.03079
Lights off	0.2463***	-0.0103	0.0987**	0.0007
Less wash. mach.	0.0655	0.0945*	-0.0742	-0.1023*
Less tumble dryer	0.2093***	0.0831	-0.0435	0.0396
Less dishwasher	0.0720	0.0367	-0.0586	-0.0933*
Less hot showers	0.1169**	0.0551	-0.1277**	-0.0444
Wash def. hrs	0.1532***	0.0872*	-0.0567	0.0078
Dry def. hrs	0.2331***	0.0035	-0.0605	0.0267
Dishes def. hrs	0.1713***	0.0275	-0.0521	-0.0455
Showers def. hrs	0.0660	0.0171	-0.1378**	-0.0666

Notes: ERFL = Energy-related financial literacy. PEL = Perceived energy literacy. FL = Financial literacy. EL = Energy literacy.
Significance: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

D. Regression Tables from the interaction model

Here, we present the full regression results for the averaged PBC model with the environmental attitude \times income interaction, extending the main results and including all control variables. Table X reports the complete estimates, highlighting the direct effects of pro-environmental attitudes, age, income, and other socio-demographics on perceived behavioural control (PBC). Pro-environmental attitudes and age consistently show strong positive associations with PBC, while higher income decreases it; the interaction term remains non-significant, indicating no moderating role of income on the attitude-PBC relationship.

TABLE X
REGRESSION RESULTS FROM PROENV \times INCOME INTERACTION MODEL

Coefficients	Estimate
Env. attitude	0.14703***
PEL	0.04562
ERFL	-0.06980*
Income	-0.10393***
Hours at home	-0.01596
Household size	-0.04335
Age of building	0.07391*
Age	0.19501***
Gender	0.05364
Education	-0.08122**
Env. attitude : Income	0.03033

Notes: ERFL = Energy-related financial literacy. PEL = Perceived energy literacy.
Significance: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

E. Complete Regression Tables

Here, we present the full regression results for all models, extending Table II and including all control variables and literacy measures. In Table XI reports the estimates for the model using the composite ERFL index, whereas Table XII separates ERFL into FL and EL to assess their individual contributions. Together, these tables provide a comprehensive overview of how literacy variables and control factors influence perceived behavioural control (PBC) and the likelihood of engaging in specific energy-saving behaviours. Across all actions, environmental attitudes consistently show strong positive associations with PBC, while age increases and income decreases perceived ease, whereas the literacy variables, whether combined or separated, remain largely non-significant except for a few isolated behaviours.

TABLE XI
REGRESSION RESULTS WITH ALL VARIABLES (N=804)

Action	Env. attitude	PEL	ERFL	Age	Income	Hours home	HH size	Bldg age	Gender	Educ.
Total PBC	0.1227***	0.0234	-0.0411	0.1933***	-0.131***	-0.0032	-0.009	0.0556	0.0429	-0.0556
Turning off lights	0.1937***	-0.0258	0.11252**	-0.0223	-0.0357	0.0944*	-0.0266	0.0281	0.0637	0.0173
Less washing machine	0.0282	0.0521	-0.0979*	0.2044***	-0.2148***	-0.0981	-0.10*	0.1013*	0.0664	-0.10*
Tumble dryer	0.1648**	0.0585	0.045562	0.2074***	-0.1642**	-0.1234*	-0.0134	0.1010*	0.1529**	-0.005
Dishwasher	0.0323	0.0312	-0.1085*	0.2989***	-0.2003***	-0.0552	-0.0016	0.0283	0.003	-0.1008*
Reduce hot showers	0.1085*	0.0258	-0.1288*	0.1618**	-0.1397**	-0.0547	-0.0476	0.073*	-0.0436	-0.0419
Defined hours wash clothes	0.1479**	0.0735*	-0.0117	0.2029***	-0.0815	0.02	-0.0393	0.011	0.054	-0.0464
Defined hours tumbler dryer	0.2272***	0.0035	-0.01689	0.2555***	-0.0765	-0.006	-0.002	0.0498*	0.0916*	-0.0189
Defined hours washing dishes	0.1633***	0.012	-0.031	0.1857***	-0.1444**	-0.0004	-0.0471	0.0235	0.0002	-0.1245*
Defined hours hot showers	0.0392	0.0199	-0.133*	0.2451***	-0.1217*	-0.072	-0.0408	0.0843*	0.002	-0.08

Notes: Significance: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.

TABLE XII
REGRESSION RESULTS WITH ALL VARIABLES (N=804)
Model separating ERFL

Action	Env. attitude	PEL	FL	EL	Age	Income	Hours home	HH size	Bldg age	Gender	Educ.
Total PBC	0.1236***	0.0225	-0.033	-0.0189	0.1951***	-0.1298***	-0.003	-0.009	0.0562	0.0423	-0.0781**
Turning off lights	0.191***	-0.0224	0.1006*	0.04361	-0.0289	-0.04	0.09423*	-0.0269	0.0259	0.0658	-0.013
Less washing machine	0.028	0.0528	-0.0433	-0.0727	0.2032***	-0.2157***	-0.0981	-0.10*	0.101*	0.0668	-0.1009*
Tumble dryer	0.1689***	0.0743	-0.0312	0.0742	0.2116***	-0.1585**	-0.1232*	-0.0138	0.1039*	0.1501**	-0.009
Dishwasher	0.032	0.0318	-0.0494	-0.0795	0.2977***	-0.2011***	-0.0553	-0.0015	0.0279	0.003	-0.1016*
Reduce hot showers	0.1123*	0.0472	-0.1186*	-0.0472	0.1699**	-0.1344**	-0.0549	-0.0472	0.0757	-0.04626	-0.0366
Defined hours wash clothes	0.1486**	0.073*	-0.016	0.0002	0.2044***	-0.05366	-0.0204	-0.0392	0.0116	0.0537	-0.0453
Defined hours tumbler dryer	0.2299***	0.0006	-0.0448	0.0169	0.2612***	-0.0728	-0.0062	-0.002	0.0518	0.0898*	-0.0151
Defined hours washing dishes	0.1611***	0.0144	-0.0133	-0.0443	0.181***	-0.1475**	-0.0003	-0.0473	0.0219	0.0013	-0.1275*
Defined hours hot showers	0.0419	0.0229	-0.1066	-0.0612	0.2509***	-0.1179*	-0.0722	-0.0405	0.0863	0.003	-0.0762*

Notes: Significance: *** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$.